

Philosophy and anthropology: A meta-critique of anthropological thought

Like any other discipline, the way anthropologists think about the world is informed and shaped by oft unexamined underlying assumptions about how we *believe* the world operates and how people in the world (ought to) behave. These assumptions are not random, but rather result from carefully and systematically organized scholarship that first proposes a novel way of understanding human organization, after which subsequent generations of adherents take it upon themselves to build or add to or challenge. Eventually, these exercises diverge into differing camps of theoretical production across disciplines and within disciplines themselves. In this course, our objective will be to analyze how different grounding/guiding assumptions of what we mean by foundational concepts (like *culture/Culture* or the *human*) lead to different, both competing and complementary, ways of predicting and postulating on our social worlds.

This course adopts what philosopher Lewis Gordon has referred to as a metacritique of reason, and will focus on how different thinkers have defined the human, freedom, and the evaluative parameters to justify both. This course will start with so-called classical thinkers in the social sciences, moving through more contemporary philosophers and historians, on to the Black Radical tradition. The course will end with a cursory examination of emerging neo-reactionary philosophy. This course has two main objectives. First, this course intends to demonstrate how our underlying (preliminary) definitions of humanity and our assumptions of the ultimate goal of being human impact how we view the constitution of social organization and how this impacts our ultimate analysis. Second, this course will invite students to examine these oft unexamined underlying assumptions to then question the specious deterministic reasoning that informs contemporary right-wing rhetoric promulgated particularly by neo-accelerationist libertarians. The thinkers compiled in this course are not meant to be exhaustive (nor exclusive to anthropology) but indicative of how some social theorists theorize within explicit philosophical traditions.

1. Week 1: A meta-critique of anthropology

- a. Gordon, Lewis R. 2010. «Theory in Black: Teleological suspensions in philosophy of culture». *Qui Parle* 18 (2): 193-214.
- b. Harvey, Sandra. 2021. «Unsettling Diasporas: Blackness and the Spectre of Indigeneity». *Postmodern Culture* 31 (1/2).

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<https://www.pomoculture.org/2021/09/16/unsettling-diasporas-blackness-and-the-specter-of-indigeneity/>.

- c. Das, Veena, Michael Jackson, Arthur Kleinman, y Bhri Gupta Singh. 2014. *The Ground Between: Anthropologists Engage Philosophy*. North Carolina: Duke University Press. (Introduction, ch 1, 2, 6, 12)

2. Week 2: Marxism and anthropology

- a. Marx, Karl. 1973. *Grundrisse: Foundations of the Critique of Political Economy*. Penguin Books. (Selections)
- b. <https://www.marxists.org/archive/marx/works/1857/grundrisse/index.htm>.
- c. Taussig, Michael. 1983. *The Devil and Commodity Fetishism in South America*. North Carolina: University of North Carolina Press.

3. Week 3: Interpretivism: Weber and Bourdieu and Ghassan Hage

- a. Weber, Max. s. f. *Conceptos sociológicos fundamentales*. Joaquín Abellán García. Madrid: Alianza editorial.
- b. Bourdieu, Pierre. 1977. *Outline of a Theory of Practice*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- c. Hage, Ghassan. 2015. *Alter-politics: Critical anthropology and the radical imagination*. Melbourne: Melbourne University Press.

4. Week 4: Polanyi and the substantivist school

- a. Polanyi, Karl. 2001. *The Great Transformation: The Political and Economic Origins of Our Time*. Boston: Beacon Press.
- b. Bear, Laura. 2015. *Navigating Austerity: currents of debt along a South Asian River*. Stanford: Stanford University Press.

5. Week 5: Nietzsche – Michel Foucault and the bio-nouns

- a. Nietzsche, Friedrich. 2006. *Nietzsche: On the Genealogy of Morality*. Keith Ansell-Pearson. Cambridge Texts in the History of Political Thought. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. (selections)
- b. Foucault, Michel. 1978. *The History of Sexuality: The Will to Knowledge*. New York: Pantheon Books. (selections)

- c. Grosfoguel, Ramón. 2012. «El concepto de “racismo” en Michel Foucault y Frantz Fanon: ¿teorizar desde la zona del ser o desde la zona del no-ser?» *Tabula Rasa*, n.º 16, 79-102.
- d. Garcia, Angela. 2010. *The Pastoral Clinic: Addiction and Dispossession along the Rio Grande*. California: University of California Press.

Or

Petryna, Adriana. 2013. *Life Exposed: Biological Citizens after Chernobyl*. Princeton: Princeton University Press.

6. Week 6: Wittgenstein and Veena Das

- a. Wittgenstein, Ludwig. 1918. *Tratado Lógico-filosófico*. The Ludwig Wittgenstein Project.
<https://books.wittgensteinproject.org/pdf/spanish/Tratado%20%C3%B3gico-filos%C3%B3fico.pdf>.
- b. Cavell, Stanley. 1988. *In Quest of the Ordinary: Lines of Skepticism and Romanticism*. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press.
<https://archive.org/details/inquestofordinar00cave>.
- c. Das, Veena. 2020. *Textures of the Ordinary: Doing Anthropology After Wittgenstein*. New York: Fordham University Press.

7. Week 7: Contra-Foucault: Feminist theory on the Sovereign

- a. Butler, Judith. 1997. *The Psychic Life of Power: Theories in Subjection*. Stanford: Stanford University Press. (selected chapters)
- b. Povinelli, Elizabeth. 2011. *Economies of Abandonment: Social Belonging and Endurance in Late Liberalism*. North Carolina: Duke University Press.
- c. Puar, Jasbir. 2015. «The “Right” to Maim: Disablement and Inhumanist Biopolitics in Palestine». *Borderlands* 14 (1): 1-27.

8. Week 8: Radical Phenomenology

- a. Gordon, Lewis. 1995. *Fanon and the Crisis of European Man: An Essay on Philosophy and the Human Sciences*. Great Britain: Routledge.
- b. Julia, Suárez-Krabbe. 2015. *Race, Rights and Rebels: Alternative to Human Rights and Development from the Global South*. Maryland: Rowman and Littlefield Publishers.

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9. Week 9: Hortense Spillers and Cultural vestibularity

- a. Spillers, Hortense. 2003. *Black, White, and in Color: Essays on American Literature and Culture*. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press. (selected chapters)
<https://archive.org/details/blackwhiteincolo0000spil/page/n5/mode/2up>.
- b. Campt, Tina, dir. 2014. *Black Feminist Futures and the Practice of Fugitivity*. Helen Pond McIntyre '48 Lecture. Barnard Center for Research on Women.
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2ozhqw840PU>.
- c. Campt, Tina. 2017. *Listening to Images*. North Carolina: Duke University Press.

10. Week 10: Sylvia Wynter on Man

- a. Wynter, Sylvia. 1984. «The Ceremony Must be Found: After Humanism». *boundary 2* 12 (3): 19-70.
- b. Wynter, Sylvia. 2003. «Unsettling the Coloniality of Being/Truth/Freedom: Towards the Human, After Man, Its Overrepresentation--An Argument». *The New Centennial Review* 3 (3): 257-337.
- c. Wynter, Sylvia. 2015. «The Ceremony Found: Towards the Autopoietic Turn/Overturn, its Autonomy of Human Agency and Extraterritoriality of (Self-)Cognition». En *Black Knowledges/Black Struggles: Essays in Cultural Epistemology*, Ambrose, J. and Sabine Broeck, 181-245. Liverpool University Press.
- d. Edu, Ugo Felicia. 2025. «Anthropological knowledge under redaction: Meditations on race, health, and aesthetics». *Medical Anthropology Quarterly* 38 (4): 462-76. <https://doi.org/10.1111/maq.12793>.
- e. Bailey, M., y W. Peoples. 2017. «Towards a Black Feminist Health Science Studies». *Catalyst: Feminism, Theory, Technoscience* 3 (2): 1-27.
- f. Chari, Sharad. 2024. *Apartheid Remains*. North Carolina: Duke University Press.

11. Week 11: Batailles and the neo-reactionaries

- a. Bataille, Georges. 1988. *The Accursed Share: An Essay on General Economy*. Vol. I Consumption. New York: Zone Books.
- b. Land, Nick. 2012. *Fanged Noumena: Collected Writing 1987-2007*. Robin Mackay and Ray Brassier. UK: MPG Books Group.
<https://archive.org/details/fangednoumena/page/n5/mode/2up>.
- c. TBD (Forthcoming Beth Gaglia)